

Socio-Political Exploration of Sorting and Sex for Grade in the Nigerian Education System

¹**Arinze Thankgod Okpala**

Social Sciences Unit, School of General Studies, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus/
Department of Social & Political Science, University of Chester, UK
Email: arinze.okpala@unn.edu.ng

^{2*}**Chidi Philip Okorie***

Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Faculty of the Social Sciences,
University of Nigeria, Nsukka
Email: chidiphilip1994@gmail.com

³**Esq Pius Elot Etan**

Nigeria Police Force, Enugu State Police Command
Email: piuseliot16@gmail.com

Abstract

This article explores how sorting and sex for grade undermine Nigerian education system. The tertiary institution's significance in the development of human capital places it in a good position to guarantee the accomplishment of this national aim. Many unscrupulous practices are said to plague university education in Nigeria. Sorting and sexual harassment have been identified as major public crisis that significantly hinders development and education. . Sexual harassment and extortion of various kinds are perceived the worst forms of corruption growing steadily on university campus in recent years. This may come in various forms such as selling of substandard reading materials, selling of continuous assessment grades to highest bidders and sorting of examination grades. It is in this note that the article calls for counsellors in the universities to organize seminars/symposia and workshops in enlightening the university community on good moral and ethical standards that help to prevent academic corruption especially based on examination ethics once in a semester, using orientation programmes.

Keywords: Ethical standards, National development, Sex for grade, Socio-political exploration,

Sorting

1. Introduction

Adopting and passing down the proper values from generation to generation is one of the components required to attain the goal of sustainable development. The tertiary institution's significance in the development of human capital places it in a good position to guarantee the accomplishment of this national aim. Tertiary education, as defined by Nwangwu (2007), is the education provided in universities, polytechnics, colleges of education, and other institutions that offer correspondence courses, following secondary education. The critical role which tertiary institutions should play in our national development is vividly summarized in the National Policy on Education (2004) among others, as: to contribute to national development through relevant high -level manpower training, to develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of society, to promote scholarship, community service, national unity and international understanding.

Admin (2012) noted that bribery and corruption have unofficially gained legitimacy at Nigerian universities, where non-academic workers, academic staff, senior lecturers, and even professors are entangled in the web of corruption. According to Nta (2012), the Independent Corrupt Practice Commission (ICPC) has persisted in bemoaning the ways in which corruption has stunted creativity, minimised the importance of diligence, and elevated mediocrity within the country's higher education system. He added that some university teachers in Nigeria have sunk into the shameful abyss or moral decadence, becoming sex bullies as a result of their unbridled lust for female undergraduates they are paid to teach. He asserted that education is directly responsible for developing strong character, and universities are set up to push forward the frontiers of knowledge, transform people's lives and contribute to health and wealth of our nation through their deep involvement in wider society and the economy. He expressed his

dismay when he said that it is sad that the citadel of learning has become havens for sex perverts (Nta, 2012). He warned that we must be vigilant to nip in the bud all corrupt practices in teaching research and community development programmes in order to maintain the required academic standards that will guarantee national development and global competitiveness.

There are various degrees of corrupt practices. For instance Nta (2013) reported that from petitions from students, members of staff, unions and other stakeholders, corrupt practices in the university system include: admission racketeering, examination misconduct, falsification of academic records such as transcripts, sexual harassment or sex for grade and victimization of applicants, victimization of students by officials, lack of commitment to work by lecturers, syndicated plagiarism by students and staff, delay or non-payment of gratuities and pension to pensioners and non-adherence to bidding processes in award of contracts. Others include sorting, illegal accreditation, running unapproved courses, etc. Sequel to the academic corruption in the campuses, students have devised other means to please their lecturers such as keeping close relationship, running errand for lecturers, visitation to their offices daily, speaking the same dialect, buying expensive gifts for lecturers' birthday or for any member of the family, attending the same fellowship or church among others to influence grades. Causes of sorting have been identified to include university admitting students into courses they know nothing about (Osunde, 2012) and general moral decadence and high premium place on certificates (Ejiogu, 2001). Others include greed, poverty and over ambitious craze for wealth.

The rate of sorting in Nigerian universities has become worrisome especially when those (university managers and administrators) who are to manage it are involved Chukwu, & Lato, 2016). Osunde (2012) defined sorting as a system through which deficient students engage in

gratification of their lecturers with items such as money, expensive gifts and even sex in the case of female students, in order to obtain good grades in examinations. Orizu (2014) observed that corruption on the part of administrators, academic staff and non-academic staff, as well as students have resulted in lack of adequate infrastructures, admission racketeering, examination malpractices, sorting of courses, politicization and falsification of academic records such as transcripts, fraudulent allocation of degree results, actual misappropriation of funds, sexual harassment and victimization as well as syndicated plagiarism by students and lecturers in tertiary institutions.

It has been observed that course coordinators or Reps act as agent to such lecturers and at times, they persuade their course mates to sort for the courses in order to get good grades (Admin, 2014). It has also been noted that lecturers use this medium to extort money and exploit students. In some instances, even after sorting the student may still fail. Admin (2014) observed that students who intend to sort their courses after examination stay back in school and at times lecturers do disappoint at the end of the day such that after paying the required amount, there is still the probability that the student may fail or get a ridiculous grade. Some lecturers will refuse to collect money from the females but demand for sex. Nta (2013) opined that sexual harassment seems to rank extremely very high among corrupt practices uncovered in the universities. He wondered why universities which should uphold the sterling values of the society is enmeshed with horrible misconduct on campus.

The phenomenon of sex for marks is not a new concept in the educational system, particular in higher institutions. It is a situation whereby teachers (lecturers inclusive) take undue advantage of students to have sexual relationship with them with the promise to positively

influence their scores in an examination. Students also offer sex to lecturers in order to boost their scores. Sex for marks takes two forms: one is comically referred to as STD (Sexually Transmitted Degree), here, female students throw themselves sexually at male lecturers for better grades in their individual courses. The sex is initiated by the female students for academic favour. The other form is the most controversial, here, the male lecturers sexually exploits struggling female students. They prey on female students that are struggling academically and sexually exploit them by offering them better grades in exchange for sexual relationship with them (Ogummokun, 2019). According to Bakari and Leachm (2008); and Arogundade (2019), Sex-for-marks also known as 'transactional sex', 'sexually transmitted grades', the quid pro quo' is a product of sexual harassment that involved giving sexual favours to male lecturers in exchange for marks or grades which has the tendency of creating an anxious campus climate. Some lecturers demand for sexual favour from their students in return for grades/marks. This article explores the socio-political exploration of how sorting and sex for grade undermine Nigerian education

2. Conceptual explanation of sorting

Sorting is a process by which students pay in cash or kind to be awarded unmerited marks by lecturers after an examination or test (Chukwu & Lato, 2016). Osunde (2012) defined sorting as a system through which deficient students engage in the gratification of their lecturers with items such as money, expensive gifts, and even sex in the case of female students, in order to obtain good grades in examinations. He further observed that some lecturers frustrate students by refusing to cooperate, making them have carry-overs, extensions, missing scores, and even poor

grades because of their failure to sort. Admin (2014) sees sorting as a situation where students liaise with their lecturers and other officials to inflate grades in exchange for money or other forms of gratification. Sorting, also known as 'runs' or 'blocking', has become a campus culture in universities, such that a student will never graduate if he or she fails to sort or pay the project supervisor or invigilator. The situation has gone so bad that there is hardly a graduate from a Nigerian university who has never sorted in one way or another. Various tactics are adopted by lecturers to arm-twist students: irregular attendance of lectures, teaching a very large class without a public address system, announcing through the course representative (Course Rep) that anyone who pays a certain amount will get an extra mark, and setting questions out of the course contents. These are just a few of the methods used by lecturers to manipulate students. This trend has compelled students to keep a good proportion of their upkeep allowance from their parents for that purpose.

3. Sex for grade: a global trend

Sex in exchange for marks in universities and other higher institutions is a global issue. Morley and Lussier (2009) and Onoyase (2019) opined that sex-for-marks is a global problem that has permeated the fabrics of higher institutions and many work places where human beings interact. Okebukola (2018) confirmed a growing trend of sex-for-marks cases in universities worldwide, emphasizing the urgent need for thorough investigation and sanctions to curb this phenomenon. These submissions appear to be the truth, as evidence abounds. Olakunle and Agboola (2020) submitted that Sex for Marks syndrome is not limited to Nigeria alone; it cuts across some parts of Africa (Ghana, South Africa, Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, Namibia, and

Egypt). We have gathered a lot of information from the tertiary institutions in these countries, and we found out that there is a high level of sexual abuse and molestation of students by their lecturers.

Kenyatta University (KU), one of Kenya's largest higher learning institutions, located in Kahawa, Nairobi; the School of Computing and Information Technology at Makerere University; Kyambogo University, Uganda (where a lecturer at the faculty of engineering was accused of demanding sex from female students in exchange for good marks); and Islamic University in Uganda, IUIU (when 23 students were suspended for a year for reportedly indulging in sex-for-marks activities while on campus). The United States' Brown University, the University of Malawi in Morocco, Columbia University (Channels Television, 2021, Trumpet News, 2021, and Al Jazeera Media Network, 2021), and the School of Computing and Information Technology at Makerere University are just a few examples.

4. Consequences of sex for grades

The evils associated with sexual exploitation and gender-based violence are legion and staggeringly harmful, both to the victim and to society at large (Udechukwu et al., 2020). A victim of rape or other sexual abuse loses their self-worth; they suffer acute mental torture and psychological humiliation. In addition to being susceptible to contracting venereal and other sexual diseases, One cannot rule out unwanted pregnancies, truncated academic careers, depression, and even suicide. Some writers describe it as exploitation. Right inside the campuses, sex for grade students' moves around with the air and swagger of having superiority complexes and looks down on their studious counterparts. TThey move around with a lot of confidence and

exhibit braggadocio, implying that regardless of whether they study their books or not, they must pass their examinations. As a result, they go to parties, travel for weekends, and, of course, sleep for hours when they are supposed to study their books, do their assignments, and other tasks.

On a societal level, the graduation of sex-for-marks students would essentially release a group of ignorant and unqualified professionals into society, akin to committing a homicide. The society, including the perpetrators of this debased and dishonourable act, as well as their offspring and relatives, will suffer greatly as a result, as it is akin to throwing stones into a marketplace (Madubuko, 2019) In their study, Taiwo et al. (2014) found that some of the psychological impacts of sexual harassment include, but are not limited to, the fact that sexual harassment undermines the integrity of the academic environment and prevents its victims from achieving their full potential. For instance, graduates with certificates obtained through sex-for-grades or sexual consent are not worth the certificates they have been conferred with. This is clearly demonstrated in the performance of the half-baked graduates who have recently entered the labor market.

5. Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework for this exploratory study is strain theory, as propounded by Smelser (1993). This theory is also known as structural strain theory. This theory considers structural strain to be the underlying factor contributing to collective behavior. Structural strain may occur at different levels, such as norms, values, mobility, situational facilities, etc. Because of these structural strains, some generalised belief that seeks to provide an explanation for the strain may emerge. This generalised belief requires precipitating factors to trigger a collective

action. Structural-strain theory proposes six factors that encourage collective action (Smelser 1962):

(a) Structural conduciveness: In this context, people tend to perceive their society as having issues. In the context of this study, people may think that art is not in line with their cultural beliefs and practices.

(b) structural strain: people experience deprivation as a result of their condition. In this case, people may begin to experience stigmatisation as a result of the mode through which they were born in their immediate society.

(c) The growth and spread of a solution: People propose and spread solutions to the problems they face. A solution, such as structural stigma or ostracism, may be suggested in the context of this study.

(d) precipitating factors: This solution is targeted as a catalyst for public display. We target events like traditional ceremonies and rituals.

(e) Lack of social control: In the absence of social control or institutional mechanisms, the solution will become evident, and in the case of this study, stigmatisation may ensue. If action is quickly and powerfully repressed, it may never materialize.

(f) Mobilization: This refers to the proactive aspect of collective behavior, where individuals take necessary actions. In this case, people began to expressly profess that a particular person or group of people are not truly sons of the soil.

This theory therefore suggests that whether or not a person engages in crime is dependent on the way in which society is structured. This theory is also subject to circular reasoning as it incorporates, at least in part, deprivation theory and relies upon it, as well as social and structural strain, for the underlying motivation for collective behaviour.

6. Conclusion and recommendations

Rising corruption news from the nation's many higher institutions are not pleasant to the ears. Frequently, scandals of numbing proportions ring out making the headlines. Lecturers are heard demanding sex for marks from their female students. The students are heard paying their teachers for good grades, while lecturers are forcing students to buy their handouts. Sexual harassment, extortion of various kinds, is perceived as one of the worst forms of corruption growing steadily on university campus in recent years. This may come in various forms such as selling of substandard reading materials, selling of continuous assessment grades to highest bidders and sorting of examination grades. It is in this note that the article calls for counsellors in the universities to organize seminars/symposia and workshops in enlightening the university community on good moral and ethical standards that help to prevent academic corruption especially based on examination ethics once in a semester, using orientation programmes.

References

- Nwangwu, I. O. (2007). Higher Education for Self-reliance. Imperative for the Nigerian Economy. In J.B. Babalola, G. O. Akpa, A. O. Ayeni and S.O. Adedeji (Eds). *Access, Equity in higher education*. NAEAP Publication
- Nta, E. (2012). Corrupt practices: *why ICPC targets varsities*. Retrieved from: <http://www.vanguardngr.com>

- Admin (2014). Uncial VC battles corruption. Retrieved from: <http://campusdelight.org/campus/unical-battle-corruption/>
- Nta, E. (2013). *ICPC on corruption in universities*. Retrieved from: <http://www.punchng.com/editorial/icpc-on-corruption>
- Osunde, A. (2012). Nigerian universities and sorting: what are your views? Retrieved from: <http://www.nairaaland.com>
- Chukwu, C. L., & Lato, E. T. (2016). Perception of students on 'sorting' in Nigerian universities. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Academic Excellence*, 16(1), 2141 – 3215
- Anebi, J. N. P., & Igwebuikwe, F. U. (2020). Curbing cases of extortion among academics in tertiary institutions for sustainable national development in Nigeria. *Nigerian Social Science Education Review*, 4(1), 77-87.
- Orizu, J. (2014). Political science project topic: corruption and crises of tertiary education in Nigeria. Retrieved from: <http://www.legacytechnologies.com.ng/-item?item-id>
- Bakari, S., & Leach, F. (2008). "I invited her to my office': Normalising Sexual Violence in a Nigerian College of Education". In M. Dunne (Ed.) *Gender, Sexuality and Development. Education and Society in Sub-Saharan Africa*. Rotterdam/Taipei, Sense, 71-83.
- Arogundade, O.T (2019). The psychological appraisal of campus climate and its implication on 'sex for marks' syndrome. *Journal of Behavioural Studies*. 1(1): 60-70.
- Ogunmumkun, A. (2019). *Sex for marks: An Age Long Practice in Nigerian Higher Institutions*. Retrieved from: www.BusinessDay.com.
- Onoyase, A (2019). Prevalence of Sexual Harassment of Female Students of Tertiary Education in Taraba State, North East Nigeria: Implications for Counselling. *International Journal of Higher Education*. 8(1): 77-83.
- Okebukola, P. (2018). *Saving Nigeria from Itself: Towards a Redemption Plan for Education*. 50th Anniversary Lecture of Faculty of Education, University of Ibadan, Ibadan Nigeria
- Al Jazeera (2021). *The movement tackling sexual harassment at Kenya's universities*. Al Jazeera Media Network
- Taiwo, M.O. Omole, O.C, Omole, B. T., and O.E. (2014). Sexual harassment and psychological consequences among students in higher education institutions in Osun State, Nigeria
- Madubuko, T. (2019). *Sex-for-grades: A call for stiffer penalty*. Nigeria: The Christian Outlook